

Dr Martin Holdgate,
The Nature Conservancy,
19 Belgrave Square,
London S W 1,
ENGLAND.

Dear Dr Holdgate,

I used to correspond with Dr Worthington about various problems (I was formerly in the Uganda Game Department), but I see that you have now taken over from him, and I hope therefore that you will not mind my writing to you instead.

I enclose herewith particulars of a vacancy we have at present for a Game Warden to take charge of the proposed new Simien Mountains National Park in Northern Ethiopia. It occurs to me that you might know of someone who is suitably qualified, and who would be interested in such a job?

It is most urgent that we find a man for this post as we must start work on the development of this Park as soon as the rainy season is over.--Anything you may be able to do to assist would be greatly appreciated.

I expect that you will be attending the IUCN General Assembly later this month, and I hope that I shall have an opportunity of meeting you then.

Yours sincerely,

J.H. Blower
Senior Game Warden.

JHB/mk